

Psychosocial Coaching and Mentoring Practices and Challenges of School Heads in the Division of Zambales

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Abstract: This research study explored the aspects of Psychosocial Coaching and Mentoring Practices and Challenges of School Heads in the Division of Zambales. It was conducted among Secondary School Heads and Teachers of the Department of Education, Division of Zambales. The study utilized a descriptive quantitative research design, with a survey questionnaire as a research instrument, and descriptive and inferential statistics for data analysis of data in order to determine the practices and challenges of the two groups of respondents as the basis of crafting the model. Study findings revealed that majority of the school head respondents highly practiced psychosocial coaching and mentoring. In contrast, most teacher respondents reported that their school heads highly practiced psychosocial coaching and mentoring. In addition, there is a high negative correlation between psychosocial coaching and mentoring techniques and challenges as perceived by teachers. The conceptualized model aimed at reducing challenges in psychosocial coaching and mentoring of school heads. School heads may consider maintaining a safe and hazardous environment as an agent of taking community needs as a priority.

making them more effective and meaningful. Education provides the basis for developing the human capital skills to accomplish strategic goals. As such, education must be fundamental. Successful schools result from governance demonstrated by the school heads in collaborative partnerships with relevant stakeholders (Aquino et al., 2021).

The Department of Education encourages school heads to devote most of their time to instructional leadership. One of the major responsibilities of school heads is to conduct coaching and mentoring to teachers' teaching performance as based in Republic Act No.9155. This includes coaching and mentoring teachers on the delivery of instruction. Hence, school heads should think of ways to equip teachers to deliver leather so that the school head indirectly influences learners' academic performance (Buendicho, 2018).

Coaching and mentoring involve more than just introducing a new employee to be more productive and skilled within his position in the organization. It has been proven to be critical methods of development and learning used to bring about change, develop efficiency, raise awareness, and change attitudes and behaviors in organizations (Hilali et al., 2020). Coaching and mentoring are two strategies for continuous development, parallel staff needs, and daily routine duties.

Keywords: psychosocial coaching, mentoring practices.

1. Introduction

All government and non-government institutions worldwide are concerned with advancing their educational system and

Table 1
Summary on the psychosocial coaching and mentoring practices of school heads

Dimensions	Overall Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Rank
1 Conduct of Psychosocial support	3.68	Highly Practiced	6
2 Communicating school's mission	3.72	Highly Practiced	5
3 Planning	3.79	Highly Practiced	1
4 Managing instructional program	3.74	Highly Practiced	3
5 Improving school climate	3.76	Highly Practiced	2
6 Maintaining positive working and learning environment	3.72	Highly Practiced	4
Grand Mean	3.74	Highly Practiced	

Table 2
Summary on the psychosocial coaching and mentoring practices of school heads as described by teachers

Dimensions	Overall Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Rank
1 Conduct of Psychosocial support	3.31	Highly Practiced	6
2 Communicating school's mission	3.44	Highly Practiced	5
3 Planning	3.47	Highly Practiced	2
4 Managing instructional program	3.45	Highly Practiced	3
5 Improving school climate	3.48	Highly Practiced	1
6 Maintaining positive working and learning environment	3.44	Highly Practiced	4
Grand Mean	3.43	Highly Practiced	

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Table 3

Summary on the psychosocial challenges during the coaching and mentoring practices of school heads

Dimensions	Overall Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Rank
1 Conduct of Psychosocial support	3.50	Highly Challenging	1.5
2 Communicating school's mission	3.47	Highly Challenging	4
3 Planning	3.46	Highly Challenging	5
4 Managing instructional program	3.50	Highly Challenging	1.5
5 Improving school climate	3.49	Highly Challenging	3
6 Maintaining positive working and learning environment	3.44	Highly Challenging	6
Grand Mean	3.48	Highly Challenging	

Table 4

Summary on the psychosocial challenges during the coaching and mentoring practices as described by teachers

Dimensions	Overall Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Rank
1 Conduct of Psychosocial support	3.26	Highly Challenging	6
2 Communicating school's mission	3.27	Highly Challenging	4.5
3 Planning	3.27	Highly Challenging	4.5
4 Managing instructional program	3.29	Highly Challenging	1.5
5 Improving school climate	3.29	Highly Challenging	1.5
6 Maintaining positive working and learning environment	3.28	Highly Challenging	3
Grand Mean	3.28	Highly Challenging	

Coaching and mentoring require much assistance to provide appropriate professionalism and the environment for development, training, capacity, and self-experience related to establishing a structure within the organization.

School heads are agents of change who contribute a significant impression on the educational milieu through their information-sharing methods, creating supportive social connections, participating in mentoring programs, and fostering progress (Aquino et al., 2021).

2. Result

It can be noted that the school head-respondents highly practiced coaching and mentoring in terms of "Planning", as manifested with the highest overall weighted mean of 3.79 (rank 1). This is followed by their practices on "Improving School Climate", with an overall weighted mean of 3.76 (rank 2); "Managing Instructional Program", with an overall weighted mean of 3.74 (rank 3); "Maintaining Positive Working and Learning Environment", with an overall weighted mean of 3.72 (rank 4); "Communicating School's Mission", with an overall weighted mean of 3.72 (rank 5); while their practices on the "Conduct of Psychosocial Support", had the lowest overall weighted mean of 3.68 (rank 6).

Overall, the teacher-respondents reported that their school heads highly practiced psychosocial coaching and mentoring manifested on the computed grand mean of 3.43. The result manifests that the teacher-respondents described their school heads highly practicing coaching and mentoring by improving their school climate and foster development of peace champions among students and teachers in the school.

It can be noted that the school head-respondents highly encountered psychosocial challenges during their coaching and mentoring practices in terms of "Conduct of Psychosocial Support" and "Managing Instructional Program", as manifested with the highest overall weighted mean of 3.50 (rank 1.5). This is followed by their challenges on "Improving School Climate", with an overall weighted mean of 3.49 (rank 3); "Communicating School's Mission", with an overall weighted mean of 3.47 (rank 4); "Planning", with an overall weighted mean of 3.46 (rank 5); while their challenges on "Maintaining

Positive Working and Learning Environment', had the lowest overall weighted mean of 3.44 (rank 6).

It can be noted that the teacher-respondents highly encountered psychosocial challenges during coaching and mentoring practices in terms of "Managing Instructional Program" and "Improving School Climate", as manifested with the highest overall weighted mean of 3.29 (rank 1.5). This is followed by their challenges on "Maintaining Positive Working and Learning Environment", with an overall weighted mean of 3.28 (rank 3); "Communicating School's Mission" and "Planning", with an overall weighted mean of 3.27 (rank 4.5); while their challenge on the "Conduct of Psychosocial Support", had the lowest overall weighted mean of 3.26 (rank 6).

The result denotes that the psychosocial coaching and mentoring practices of school heads as to improving school climate differs as to their age, civil status and no. of teachers supervised; while no substantial statistically detected difference in terms of their sex, highest educational attainment, position/designation, and years in the position and mentoring practices of school heads as to communicating school's mission as perceived by teacher-respondents differs as to their position/designation and length of service, while no substantial statistically detected difference in terms of their sex, age, civil status, and highest educational attainment.

3. Conclusion

This paper presented psychosocial coaching and mentoring practices and challenges of school heads in the division of Zambales.

References

- [1] Abarro, J. O. (2018). Factors affecting the performance of public-school teachers in the Division of Antipolo City, Philippines. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 5(11), 1284-1290.
- [2] Ahmad, A. R., Awang, M. M., & Mohamad, N. A. (2021). The role of social capital to promote soft skills among university students in facing the challenge of society 5.0 transformation. In Purnomo, Y. W. (Eds.), *Educational Innovation in Society 5.0 Era: Challenges and Opportunities*, pp. 18-26. Routledge.

- [3] Akos, P., Wasik, S. Z., McDonald, A., Soler, M., & Lys, D. (2019). The challenge and opportunity of competency-based counselor education. *Counselor Education and Supervision*, 58(2), 98-111.
- [4] Albugami, S., & Ahmed, V. (2015). Success factors for ICT implementation in Saudi secondary schools: From the perspective of ICT directors, head teachers, teachers and students. *International Journal of education and development using ICT*, 11(1).
- [5] Al Hilali, K.S., Al Mughairi, B.M., Kian, M.W., Karim, A.M., (2020). Coaching and Mentoring-Concepts and Practices in Development of Competencies: A Theoretical Perspective, *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences* 10 (1): 41-54.
- [6] Ali, Z. B. M., Wahi, W., & Yamat, H. (2018). A review of teacher coaching and mentoring approach. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(8), 504-524.
- [7] Allen, T. D., and Eby, L. T. eds., (2011). *The Blackwell handbook of mentoring: A multiple perspectives approach*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [8] Almedora, C. B., Niez, R. A., & Bantor, C. T. S. (2020), "Effectiveness of Principle-Centered Leadership and Characteristics of the School Heads in Leyte Division, Philippines," *International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology*.
- [9] Altun, B., & Sarkaya, P. Y. (2020). The actors of teacher supervision. *Journal of Human Sciences*, 17(1), 284-303.
- [10] Alupay, J.A. & Agatep, JLE (2022). Preparedness of Large Secondary Schools in the Implementation of e-learning. *International Journal of Computer Engineering in Research Trends*, Vol. 9, Issue 7, pp. 120-130, July 2022.
- [11] Arif, S., Zainudin, H. K., & Hamid, A. (2019). Influence of Leadership, Organizational Culture, Work Motivation, and Job Satisfaction of Performance Principles of Senior High School in Medan City. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal)*, 239254.
- [12] Arora, R., & Rangnekar, S. (2014). Workplace mentoring and career resilience: An empirical test. *The Psychologist-Manager Journal*, 17(3), 205.
- [13] Ayaz, M., Atta, M. A., Salaha-Ud-Din, B., & Khan, M. (2021). "Situational leadership of school heads regarding coaching style: comparative analysis of public and private school," *Elementary Education Online*, 20(3), 2398-2398.
- [14] Babedi, M. R. (2013). Psychosocial support provided by teachers to adolescent learners with behavioural and emotional problems (Doctoral dissertation, University of South Africa).
- [15] Baron, L., and Morin, L., (2009). The coach-coachee relationship in executive coaching: A field study. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 20(1), 85-106.
- [16] Beam, L. (2001). Would You Like Your Own Coach? *Nursing Homes Long Term Care Management*, 50(3), pp. 58-60.
- [17] Be?ken Ergi?i, M. (2021). How does working with and mentoring student teachers shape teacher educators' professional identity? In Shagrir, L., & Bar-Tal, S. (Eds.), *Exploring professional development opportunities for teacher educators*, pp. 128-142. Routledge.
- [18] Berk, L. (2002). *Child Development* (5th ed.). Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- [19] Bess, J. L., & Dee, J. R. (2012). *I am understanding college and university organization: Theories for effective policy and practice*. Stylus publishing, llc.
- [20] Bianco-Mathis, V. E., Nabors, L. K., & Roman, C. H. (2002). *Leading from the inside out: A coaching model*. California: Sage.